

IDENTIFYING SMARTPHONE CONSUMER PREFERENCES IN A CHANGING TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

Purpose – To figure out the factors that impact purchase intention of technological devices in a technology changing world. The role of loyalty of consumers versus common purchase intention factors.

Methodology/approach - Initial data from this study were collected from 126 respondents. The responses obtained were analyzed by several statistical tools, such as descriptive statistics, joint empirical distributions, and multinomial regression analysis.

Findings – As age increases, people feel that their smartphone devices are complicated to use. Because of the technical difficulty, they choose to use non-advanced devices. But there are a large number of smartphones accessible to a higher age. This study revealed that brand loyalty, prices, and smartphone design influence a consumer's purchase decision on a smartphone.

Research limitations/implications – It is conducted in one country and should be expanded to other countries. The age of the respondents seems to be very crucial, so the age distribution of respondents should be enlarged., words, words.

Practical implications – This study deals with an essential issue of globalization: the loyalty of consumers to devices and producers and changing and improving technologies.

Originality/value – Identification of the significant constructs on the revealed preference of consumers in changing technology.

Key words: max. Product Life Cycle, Purchase Intention, Smartphones

Introduction

In the last decade, smartphones have revolutionized our lives in ways that go beyond how we communicate. In addition to calls, messaging, e-mail, more than two billion people worldwide use these devices to navigate, compare prices, follow the news, watch movies, listen to music, play games, commemorate vacations, and participate in social media.

As times change and technology continuously improves, businesses must get ahead of the game and take every new opportunity to improve their sales, marketing, and customer loyalty. Manufacturers need to market their products differently, make their brands more personal, and communicate with customers in new ways. One of the biggest concerns is keeping customers happy.

The lifespan of the smartphone can last up to several years. Consumers end up replacing a smartphone not primarily because it is technological wear and tear, but because they want better features such as a more durable battery, a more robust operating system, a better camera and more. From time to time, a new smartphone is launched with upgraded features from what the consumer already has. As a result, the consumer's tendency to buy a new smartphone is rising. However, the consumer cannot afford to buy a new smartphone every year, whether from Apple or the Samsung premium series.

Besides, Xiaomi launches smartphones at a low price, not necessarily high quality, and can last a long time. Their target audience is people who want to buy cheap smartphones and, as a result, will be renewed with a new device almost every year, which is very little time.

In light of the above and mainly due to the intrusion of new and advanced technologies into our lives, it was interesting to examine the factors that motivate consumers and what triggers their decision to purchase the products.

This study focuses on factors such as brand loyalty, price, social influences, age, smartphone design, and more. These factors are relative advantage, and we would like to know how they affect the motivation to purchase a smartphone from a particular brand.

The purpose of the study is to examine whether there is a relationship between the influence of factors (brand, social impact) on the consumer's final choice in light of the dynamics and technological advancement in the world of smartphones.

The study deals with brand awareness, which plays a vital role in creating buying intentions and brand loyalty.

Literature Review

The mobile phone is now considered one of the most popular gadgets in life. The advancement of information technology enables unlimited communication between people. This communication is vital to keep in touch with friends and family, allows access to e-mail, correspondence between business partners, and more (Yusuf et. al., 2015). The smartphone gives users the impression that they are constantly connected to the outside world, and therefore less alone. The physical and mental communication on mobile devices has increased. (Srivastava, 2005) Many are afraid to leave home without it and feel uncomfortable if others are looking at their messages or private things.

The consumer's buying behavior refers to selecting, purchasing, and consuming goods and services to their satisfaction. Many factors influence the decision-making process. At first, the consumer tries to find the goods he wants to purchase and brings him the most benefit, but various factors affect his purchases, such as social, cultural, economic, and more.

We review comprehensive literature describing the phenomenon of consumer purchasing intentions in light of the dynamics and technological advancement in the world of smartphones. We will try to understand the causes of this phenomenon. This review aims to expand existing knowledge on consumer behavior and examine points of interest in consumer preferences.

Brand

A brand can be defined as a name, term, symbol or design or a combination thereof, which is intended to represent the company or services of one seller or a group of sellers to distinguish them from those of competitors (Keller, 1993).

Intense competition and rapid technological developments have led companies to increase their market share by gaining more customers and protecting their market shares (Ercis et. al., 2012). The way to save their market share is to create customer loyalty, brand awareness, and customer satisfaction level to explain this later.

When the customer continues to purchase the brand even in front of the leading competitors who offer lower prices, the higher quality means that there is significant value to the brand. The customer will not change his mind. Therefore, when customers repeat one brand's purchases, we can say that they have become loyal to that brand. There are many factors related to brand awareness and perceived brand quality that can affect customer loyalty, such as brand name, logo, quality, innovation, price, design, etc. However, companies need to choose the best strategies for attracting and retaining customers to be loyal (Akkucuk & Nooshabadi, 2016).

Duration of smartphone life

Today in the smartphone industry, there is fierce competition, companies are forced to develop technological innovation and creativity due to such rapid technological advancement. When Apple launched the iPhone in 2007, it created a new smartphone market for the average consumer. Before this launch, the phones were mostly for business users. Since companies like HTC Nokia etc. are trying their best in market competition when it is difficult when there are big players in the smartphone industry like Apple and Samsung (Mohapatra, 2016).

As consumers, we buy millions of products every year. And just like us, these products have a life cycle. Older, long-term outcomes eventually become less popular, whereas the demand for newer and more modern products usually increases quickly after their launch. Since most companies understand the different stages of the product life cycle, and that the products they sell all have a limited lifespan, most will invest heavily in developing new products to ensure their business continues to grow (Mohapatra, 2016).

Our research questions that arise from the literature review are:

- (1) Does the brand name and loyalty to a brand name is a dominant factor in purchasing a technology-based device, over time.
- (2) Is the lifecycle of a smartphone among customers of smartphones differs among brands?
- (3) Are the impacts of design, quality, price, and education strong enough compared to the brand factor?

Methodology

A pilot was conducted to get an incomplete picture of the research topic, develop hypotheses and ideas on issues relevant to the research, such as: Do people develop loyalty to their smartphone brand.

The research method includes data collection using questionnaires and quantitative analysis. Since the purpose of the study is to examine whether there is a relationship between the influence of factors (brand, social impact, etc.) on the final choice of the consumer also in light of the dynamics and technological advancement in the world of smartphones.

The Questionnaire was sent to an aerospace industry organization that includes a wide variety of workers: engineers, technicians, practical engineers, managers, and manufacturing workers and students from a technological high education institute. The Questionnaire was sent to 204 persons, and we got 126 valid full responses.

We used a Multinomial regression analysis to figure out the significant factors that may impact the purchase of certain smartphone brands. We emphasize our study on three known brands, Apple, Samsung, and Xiaomi.

Findings

Some descriptive results from the survey are presented in Table 1. They are typical factors while examining technology-based devices for daily personal usage.

Table 1: Means of scores with respect to purchase intention, by brand holders

	Mean (Samsung)	Mean (Apple)	Mean (Xiaomi)
Age	40.8571	29.3548	38.1739
Years of Education	15.1964	14.7742	16.3913
Importance of Design	3.0536	4.1613	2.6522
Owning a device (Months)	19.2963	19.4516	14.3043
Impact of Brand on Perceived Quality	3.6250	3.8710	3.3043
Impact of Brand on Purchase Intention	3.7321	4.1935	2.5652
Importance of Price	4.1250	3.5161	4.4783

- Age - During the study, a wide range of ages were selected, although the average age is 36. Hence, the review is less concerned with low age, such as elementary and high school children, but we want to explain how the age factor influences the consumer when purchasing a smartphone.

Nowadays, people are digitally connected, ranging from technical issues of ordering home food to express feelings in front of electronic audiences of hundreds and thousands of people on social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, and more. The smartphone is undoubtedly a dominant and integral part of the fabric of modern life. A whole generation of children goes through adolescence with a smartphone in their hands.

According to the research findings, it could be seen that Samsung has an average age of 41.14. As a result, Samsung has an Android operating system that is simpler to use, so people of higher age will enjoy the devices Samsung offers. Compared to Apple, the average age is 30.14, which means that users' age is lower because the company has a relatively complicated operating system.

- Price -According to the research findings, it could be seen that price is a significant factor for consumers when purchasing a smartphone. But it also depends on which brand you belong to. That is, Apple has a loyal target audience willing to pay a high price tag for a very high-quality smartphone. Besides, some consumers love Samsung and are eager to pay a relatively high price for their premium devices and whether or not Samsung is introducing cheaper A-Series smartphones. That is, Samsung wants to appeal to everyone, whether it is high-class or middle-class. And finally, there's a high-tech company whose target audience is the middle / lower class, which means those consumers prefer to buy a low-priced smartphone.
- Brand loyalty - Today, brand loyalty is one of the important things for smartphone companies. They want the Israeli consumer to be loyal, in one way or another, to some brand. That is, he will continue to buy the same brand he currently uses.

Samsung's smartphone companies realized that it needed to place a low price tag that would allow consumers to continue to purchase a smartphone from Samsung and prevent its users from defecting to Chinese competitors, headlined.

According to the research findings, you could see that brand loyalty was for all three smartphone companies Samsung, Apple, and Xiaomi. It is highly likely that every customer, who has already put their trust in the name of a particular brand, will continue to purchase smartphones from the same manufacturer. Being well accustomed to this brand, the customer will find it challenging to transfer to another brand to the smartphone's satisfaction.

- Smartphone design - Smartphone design is a no less important factor than perceived brand quality or smartphone price. Nowadays, anyone who comes to purchase a smartphone checks the size, shape, button position, color, and other decorations.

According to the research findings, smartphone design is fundamental to consumers when purchasing a smartphone. Consumers understand that this is just as important as anything else, and that is why most people test the device when it is presented before purchase.

- Perceived quality of the brand - Perceived quality is a factor that can decide the consumer whether or not to buy the smartphone. Sometimes quality can be expressed in the way that customers or users believe that the product or service exceeds their needs and expectations.

Samsung and Apple are in the top spot of the smartphone quality level. Still, today it is one of the world's largest mobile manufacturers. It has become an empire of smartphones and a host of technology products.

According to the research findings, it could be seen that the Chinese company, Shiomi, was not far from Samsung and Apple's results. In other words, the consumer understands that it may be my goal with less experience in the smartphone market, but can take out an equally high-quality device from the big companies.

- Adjusting the palm size of the smartphone - When a consumer is looking for a new smartphone, it takes into consideration how it feels on the hand. In the market, we can find different sized screens, and it is up to the consumer to decide which one meets his needs.

Apple has several different size iPhones, so it is advisable to check and hold the smartphone to figure out the most convenient shape. Samsung has smartphones that have the home button on the side of the device, and some are on top of the device screen, so the size of the smartphone device is no less critical than the palm-size. Especially as the smartphone grows, the more difficult it is to navigate or type with one hand.

According to the study's findings, it didn't seem to matter to consumers whether their smartphone device would be best suited to their palm. These results are for the three smartphone companies Samsung, Apple, and Xiaomi tested during the study.

The statistical analysis includes the role of having in the past a particular brand on the respondent's current brand. We used a multinomial regression analysis to find out these magnitudes as they are provided in Table 2. Table 2 is designed to be as concise as possible to reflect the three important magnitudes.

Table 2. The estimated impact on probability to have a brand while not having it in the past.

	Samsung Now	Apple Now	Xiaomi Now		p-value
No Samsung in the past	-1.295				0.01
No Apple in the past		-4.700			0.00
No Xiaomi in the past			-3.307		0.006

The coefficients are significant. It means that a person that didn't have Samsung in the past has less probability of having Samsung now (-1.295). This is compared to Apple (-4.7) and Xiaomi (-3.307). The numbers are the coefficients from the exponential function of the multinomial part.

Discussion and conclusions

The study gives us some exciting insights and justifications to well-known facts in the smartphone industry. The loyalty of customers to their smartphone brands over time and technological changes is very high. We see that the chance of respondent to have a particular brand is much lower if he or she didn't have it in the past. This contributes to our first research question.

On average, we found that respondents who have Apple or Samsung have the same device for 19 months. And only Xiaomi holder have their device for 14.3 months on average. The no difference between Samsung and Apple is meaningful. Xiaomi is a relatively new brand, and it is relatively not expensive. This reflects our second research question.

On average, Apple holders give score 4.16 on a scale of 1 to 5, to the importance of design in smartphone purchasing, compared to Samsung (3.05) and Xiaomi (2.65).

It is inferring that typical factors that affect purchase intention are still valid in the smartphone industry. This reflects our third research question.

The added value of this study is in several concepts. The usage of smartphones in learning is desirable to students (Sadeh, Feniser, and Dusa, 2020). The rapid changes in technology affect our wellbeing feelings and smartphones are very influential.

The study has a few limitations. It is conducted in one country and should be expanded to other countries. The respondents' age seems to be very crucial, so the age distribution of respondents should be enlarged.

Notes

* This paper is based on an M.Sc. project of Sapir Shimri at HIT, Israel 2019.

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